

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL LEARNING IN CLASSROOM.

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Abstract. This article is about innovative technologies which are improving day by day. For example, electronic diaries and magazines, interactive electronic boards, computers, tablets, video cameras. Just digital learning and its importance has been clarified in this article. Also, the effectiveness of digital learning for teachers and learners is explained.

Key words: innovative, technology, digital, education, augmented reality, virtual reality, education, cooperative, Internet, communication, activity magazines, electronic boards.

Nowadays, the importance of modern technologies is increasing day by day. There is a variety of modern technology that is produced and used in educational institutions. These include computer-aided teaching, educational management systems, the Internet, virtual reality, augmented reality. We can see this especially in the field of education in the example of digital learning. Digital education is a method of education organized using innovative technologies. For example, electronic diaries and magazines, interactive electronic boards, computers, tablets, video cameras. In recent decades, great technological advances have been noted in the field of education. These innovative technologies provide new ways of learning or improve traditional learning methods.

For example, **using electronic diaries and magazines** in schools creates a number of convenience opportunities for teachers, students and parents. Parents can monitor their children's grades and how well they are learning the lesson. Pupils

will also have the opportunity to get detailed information about their results. Furthermore, digital learning has some opportunities which are in the followings:

Individualized learning. In traditionally organized classes, students have the opportunity to learn at their own pace through digital learning. that is, the lesson process is recorded and students have the opportunity to learn more and effectively through repetition and repetition. In short, teaching and learning are tailored to each student's abilities.

Cooperative. Through digital learning, students are organized to work as a team, that is, they complete the assigned task in a group, and through this, they organize cooperation that is important for their careers in the future.

Mutual communication. Usually in traditional classes, teachers explain the subject. Students ask the teacher what they don't understand. and through digital education, students have the opportunity to immediately find the answers they need through online communication with each other. Benefits for the disabled. One of the most important benefits of digital learning is the improvement of learning in general. it also provides more convenience for disabled people. Students with disabilities learn more easily in a digital learning environment than in traditional learning.

Source of information. By using digital learning, pupils have a great deal of information. Just, they can find any information on the internet. Also they can share it with each other. Furthermore, the do not have to carry heavy books or to wait in a line in libraries.

Interesting activities. In digital education, teachers can attract students to the lesson by adding various images, audios, videos and make the lesson process more interesting.

Preparation for life skills. Using innovative technologies in classrooms turned it into a unique form of literacy. Because, today we can come into using of innovative technology in every day. For example, in workplaces, educational

institutions, airports, police stations, post offices. Giving students the opportunity to teach and improve these skills prepares them for life outside the classroom.

In conclusion, the importance of digital learning in the field of education is increasing rapidly. Not only, digital learning helps to become better teaching and learning, but also, learners are able to wide their outlook. Moreover, the role of digital learning in the success in the field of education is incomparable.

Reference

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Useful sites

1. <https://drexel.edu/soe/resources/student-teaching/advice/how-to-use-technology-in-the-classroom/>
2. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-digital-learning-todays-world-siddhi-mistry>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Personalized_learning
<https://www.rocket.chat/blog/digital-education>